

Navigating Uncharted Childhood in the Absence of Parental Anchor

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Abstract

This is a qualitative study on children growing up in the absence of both parents focusing on their childhood experiences. Given that the study aimed to explore and interpret the personal experiences of children growing up without parental anchors, a phenomenological design will allow to delve deeply into their subjective experiences and the meanings they attach to these experiences. This particularly focused on the children's relationship with their parents or guardians and peers, their perceived challenges, coping mechanisms, and aspirations in life. This involved 12 orphans and LBC in Misamis Occidental aging 11 to 17 years, all attending basic education. The study employed semi-structured interviews with interview protocol developed by the researchers of this study. The findings underscore the resilience and adaptability of children facing familial adversity, highlighting the pivotal role of extended family members or guardians in providing stability, care, and guidance. While challenges such as emotional struggles and societal comparisons persist, participants demonstrate a remarkable capacity for coping and maintaining hopeful outlooks for the future.

Keywords: parental anchor, left behind children, childhood without parents, parental absence

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1. Background of the Study

One out of three Filipino youth grew up without parents according to a study conducted by the University of the Philippines Population Institute (UPPI) in 2022. It has been determined that the most prevalent reasons for growing up in the absence of biological parents are having parents' migration, separation, and death (Kabamalan, 2022).

This study aimed to determine the lived experiences of children in navigating their uncharted childhood in the absence of parental anchors. While there are existing studies on the effects of the lack of parental anchors on children's mental health, education, and social behavior, this study further aimed to understand these determined factors from the children's perspective. Furthermore, it is expected that the results would clarify the actual experiences and perceptions of children growing up apart the warmth of care from biological parents by conducting a qualitative study on select Filipino children in the province of Misamis Occidental. This focused on the children's relationships with their caregivers or guardians and peers, as well as their challenges, coping mechanisms, and aspirations in life.

This study would provide information on the childhood experiences of children raised in the absence of biological parents deprived of parental anchors. This particularly focused on the children's relationship with their parents or guardians and peers, their perceived challenges, coping mechanisms, and aspirations in life.

2. Literature Review

Various studies, both local and abroad, shed light of the effects of biological parents' absence on the different aspects of childhood and later life, particularly, in physical and mental health, social behavior, and education. Parental absence contributes to the child's wellbeing beyond what is already accounted for by conventional adverse childhood experiences, highlighting its distinct influence (Annor et al., 2024). According to UNICEF (2021), children lacking parental care may suffer enduring physical, psychological, emotional, and social harm, leading to lifelong consequences.

2.1. On Physical Health

Pajaron and colleagues (2020) explained that children of migrant parents exhibit lower rates of illness and irritability in contrast to offspring of non-migrant parents. Additionally, left behind girls are less prone to physical illness than their boy counterparts, regardless of whether they reside in households led by males or females.

However, a study in China (Jiang et al., 2023) found out that being raised without parental presence in the household can profoundly impact children's physical and mental health in later life, leading to adverse outcomes, which further expounds that compared with boys, girls are more inclined to the inequality of being cared for. Similarly, a study in the United Kingdom (Lacey et al., 2018) declared that parental absence was associated with early uptake of risky health behaviors.

Furthermore, parental care is substantially essential during infancy and childhood in mitigating the long-term negative impacts on the child's physical and mental growth and

development (Yang et al., 2022). Similarly, another study claims that girls residing in foster homes or with alternative caregivers exhibit notably higher body mass index (BMI), while psychosomatic complaints are notably elevated in families with stepparents, foster homes, and among girls living with someone else (Steppan et al., 2019).

Furthermore, additionally, a study in China by Zhou et al. (2018) declared results which suggest that the deterioration of depressive symptoms in left behind children (LBC) is attributed to reduced care, and the effect could not be mitigated by increased household income.

2.2. On Psychological Health

Parental absence during childhood is significantly correlated with adverse mental health outcomes and substance use in young adulthood, including higher odds of experiencing moderate to severe psychological distress, regardless of gender or sex (Annor et al., 2024). The emotional effects of parental migration are profound, leading many adolescents to experience profound sadness and a strong desire for physical presence (Rendeza, 2017).

Additionally, according to Fatima et al., (2021), adolescents living with guardians reported higher levels of perceived loneliness than those living with their parents. In Yang et al. (2022), a longer period of parental absence in children correlates to a higher depression score in later life. Also, parental absence increases the likelihood of children to engage in substance use (Annor et al., 2024), particularly, smoking and drinking alcohol (Lacey et al., 2018), and criminal involvement (Wasserman, 2020).

In contrast, a study (Høgenes & Daling, 2023) claims that higher levels of parental presence appear to boost life satisfaction among adolescents, with parental support acting as a mediator between perceived absence and satisfaction. It is important for parents to recognize that providing support remotely, such as through phone calls or text messages, may not have the same effect as being physically present.

Thus, being raised without both a father and a mother may reduce levels of self-esteem, life satisfaction, and happiness (Kabamalan, 2022). Consequently, it can be clarified that growing up with the parents is essential to the mental wellbeing of children.

2.3. On Academics

The study of Pajaron et al. (2020) presented promising findings that children of migrants demonstrate higher educational attainment and better study habits, with lower rates of poor grades and work involvement. Additionally, LBC residing in female headed households are less likely to achieve poor grades and more likely to reach higher grade levels. Also, in a paper of Rendeza (2017), the result show that despite lacking parental assistance with homework and facing additional responsibilities at home, left behind adolescents generally maintain good academic performance. While this might be the case, though it is quite positive in a sense, numerous studies negate such findings.

A study in Vietnam argued that children from two parent families have a better chance of enrolling at all levels of education than those from single parent families (Nguyen, 2022). While this is true to children with a parent present, it could be worse to children growing up without both. Kabamalan (2022) declared in a report that without both a father and a

mother is associated with an increased probability of early school dropout, teenage pregnancy, and cohabitation.

Moreover, children who lack both parents are significantly more prone to academic underachievement in both Chinese and mathematics compared to their peers (Fu et al., 2017). Similarly, poor educational outcome is found to be consequent to growing up without both biological, married parents (Wasserman, 2020). Furthermore, Yang et al. (2022) declared that a longer period of parental absence could result to lower test scores in mathematics.

In conclusion, while the presented corpus delineates the effects on physical, psychological and educational statuses of parental absence in children, this study will expound the perspectives on caregiver or guardian and peer relations, experienced challenges and aspired plans in life of children growing up with the absence of parental anchors.

3. Method

This is a qualitative study on children growing up in the absence of both parents focusing on their childhood experiences. Given that the study aims to explore and interpret the personal experiences of children growing up without parental anchors, a phenomenological design will allow to delve deeply into their subjective experiences and the meanings they attach to these experiences. The central tenets of both descriptive and interpretative phenomenology focus on individuals' subjective experiences, the meanings they attach to their lived experiences, and their relationship with their world (Langdridge, 2008 as cited in Alhazmi & Kaufmann, 2022).

3.1. Research Environment

This study involved orphans and LBC in Misamis Occidental. Misamis Occidental is a 2nd class province in Northern Mindanao region in the Republic of the Philippines. The province covers an area of 2,006.63 km². According to the 2020 Census of Population and Housing, it has a population of 617,333. The population density is calculated at 308 inhabitants per square kilometer (Philippines Statistics Authority, 2021). The province has three component cities and 14 municipalities. It is mostly hilly and mountainous and coastal in the eastern side.

According to a report (Bigornia, 2022), the gross provincial domestic product (GPDP) of Misamis Occidental in 2021 is valued at 111.2 billion Philippine pesos. The main contributors to the 2021 GPDP were: wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles; construction; and financial and insurance activities. Its major economic industries include agriculture, forestry and fishing, industry, and services. Hence, being a 2nd class, the province seems to be an economically fairly progressive area.

3.2. Selection of Participants

The participants of this study involved 12 children living away from their biological parents with age ranging from 11 to 17 years, all attending basic education. There were nine females and three males, coming from various family income statuses, eight studying in

public schools and four in private, and all of them live with blood relatives. Additionally, seven of the participants are in elementary school, four in junior high school, and one in senior high school.

The participants were selected through availability. Availability sampling, also known as convenience sampling, is a method of nonprobability or nonrandom sampling which involves selecting individuals from the target population based on practical considerations, such as their easy accessibility, proximity, availability, or willingness to participate at a given time, rather than through random selection (Etikan et al, 2015).

3.3. Data Gathering and Analysis

The study employed semi-structured interviews with interview protocol developed by the researchers of this study. The interview protocol was evaluated and validated with the help of the researchers' colleagues and advisers in the Graduate School Department of Saint Columban College, Pagadian City.

The participants were selected based on availability. Only identified children living without or away from their biological parents were considered. Each participant was informed to be interviewed as part of a research. An assent was presented to each participant before conducting the interview explaining the purpose of the research and that the participant may decline to participate or withdraw and discontinue participation anytime.

During the interview proper, the participant was ensured to be in a safe, comfortable and private venue. The participants were asked first with the generic questions: describe your experiences with your caregivers or guardians; how is your relationship with your peers; what challenges do you encounter as a child growing up without or away from your biological parents; how do you cope up with the challenges; and what are your dreams and future plans. Then the answers were probed by asking specific questions.

After the interview, the responses were transcribed as reported speech, not verbatim. Then the participants were informed about the transcription to confirm the accuracy of the written report.

Thematic analyses and thorough discussions were conducted among the researchers. After which, the research report was written, reviewed and readied for submission.

3.4. Ethical Considerations

This study adheres to the codes and policies for research ethics established by the Saint Columban College and to the ethical considerations set by the UK Statistics Authority (2022).

1. The use of data offers advantages for users and contributes to the public good.
2. The identity of the data subject, whether an individual or an organization, is safeguarded, with information kept confidential and secure, and the matter of consent is properly addressed.
3. The risks and limitations of new technologies are taken into account, and adequate human oversight ensures that the methods used align with established standards of integrity and quality.

4. The data used and methods employed comply with legal requirements, including the 1987 Philippine Constitution, Data Privacy Act of 2012 (RA 10173), Special Protection of Children Against Abuse, Exploitation and Discrimination Act (RA 7610), and other applicable local and international laws.
5. Public opinions are taken into account regarding the data used and the perceived advantages of the research.
6. The access, use, and sharing of data are conducted transparently and communicated to the public in a clear and accessible manner.

Moreover, the researchers took careful considerations in interviewing the participants who are children of age ranging from 11 to 16 years old. The researchers prepared an assent that emphasized that the participants should agree that their participation is optional and voluntary and that they could withdraw their participation anytime, and additionally, that their data should be used exclusively for this research. Furthermore, a parental consent was also prepared in case the participants opted to ask informed consent from their parents.

Above all, no personal identifying information was gathered and used to ensure confidentiality of and protection for the participants. It is ensured that no participant is forced, coerced, obliged, or deceived to participate in this study. Each participant was given a pseudonym.

4. Results and Findings

To protect the identity of the participants each one of them was given a pseudonym. Furthermore, the data and results presented are transcribed as reported rather than direct speech or verbatim form.

4.1. Results

Presented herein are the participants' brief biographical profile, followed by their reported responses gathered from the semi-structured interviews.

Alyssa

Alyssa is an 11-year-old female Grade 5 pupil. Since last year, her parents have entrusted her and her two brothers to her aunt, who is her mother's cousin. Due to financial constraints, her married parents were forced to work in Saudi Arabia. Fortunately, their aunt treated them well, ensuring that their educational and basic needs were covered at both school and home.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She remembered that when her parents left, her aunt took them out for dinners and outings. When she missed her parents, her aunt would notice and they would have a reassuring talk, during which she was advised to stop sobbing because her parents had left for their future.

Relationship with Peers. She has a close bond with her siblings. She sometimes reprimands her younger brother for misbehaving, and when he weeps, her aunt would recommend her to discipline him gently rather than physically punishing him. She also has a close relationship with her older brother, who treated her nicely.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She often finds herself caught up in the typical disagreements with her siblings, just like any other family, and during those times, she would sometimes feel a deep longing for her parents.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She deals with her problems by pursuing solutions on her own and accepting responsibility for her faults, expressing apologies when necessary. She would occasionally cry and confide in her aunt about her unhappiness and worries. Fortunately, her aunt is always there to encourage her through it all.

Dreams and Future Plans. She promised herself that whenever she would be financially independent and capable of helping out, she would gladly support her aunt. This commitment originated from her gratitude to her aunt for the compassion she had shown her and her siblings. It was not just about repaying a debt, it was about appreciating her aunt's love and care throughout the years. She recognized the value of family support and was motivated to repay the generosity she had received. So, when the opportunity occurs, she would seize it eagerly, confident that she could make a significant difference in her aunt's life, just as her aunt did for her.

Chloe

Chloe is a 16-year-old female in Grade 11. She has been living with her grandmother in a fair-income household since the age of six, following the death of her mother. Despite her father's estrangement from her mother's family and his lack of support, Chloe is well-supported financially and emotionally by her aunts and uncles.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She resides with her maternal grandmother, who, along with her aunts and uncles, provides for her financially. Despite the evident love from her caregiver, whom she affectionately calls "Mama," she grapples with feelings of longing and discontent. She yearns for the opportunity to have grown up with her biological parents, despite never having known her mother. Moreover, she harbors resentment toward her father, who now resides with his own family in a neighboring barangay and fails to offer any form of support.

Relationship with Peers. She lives with five cousins who are all girls of her age. Despite having no sibling, she disclosed that she was better off alone with her "mama". She always gets in quarrel with her cousins for reasons of using her clothes without permission and doing unassigned household chores. She is easy and outgoing at school and she has a lot of friends, but none would she consider as close as a sister. She claimed that she was fine on her own.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. Sometimes she feels envy with other children for having their own parents especially when there are school activities like recognition day and PTA (Parents-Teachers Association) meetings. She feels loneliness at times.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She consoles herself from loneliness and envy by telling herself that she is luckier than most of her peers that she has a loving "mama", aunts, uncles and "mommyla" (her grandmother's sister) whom she can run to anytime when she is at quarrel with her cousins at home or even when she is simply feeling lonely.

Dreams and Future Plans. She has not decided any course in college or any profession to pursue. She said that she just wanted to work abroad, any work, and live away from her hometown.

Cyrill

Cyrill is an 11-year-old male in Grade 5. For the past five years, he and his brother have been living with their aunt, their father's younger sister. This arrangement became necessary after their father was incarcerated due to drug-related issues. Cyrill's mother has been working abroad for a significant period, providing financial support from afar. Both his mother and aunt contribute to covering the household expenses, ensuring that Cyrill and his brother have a stable and supportive environment despite the challenges posed by their family's circumstances.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. He recalls his aunt's kind care for them, which includes regular meals and interesting adventures. He openly expresses his gratitude, feeling privileged because his aunt carefully looks after them, ensuring that their every need is met.

Relationship with Peers. He and his brother share a close bond, constantly engaging in humorous banter, teasing each other, and participating in various hobbies together. Their bond extends beyond the two of them; they have wonderful interactions with their cousins, which foster strong ties within the family circle.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. When he misses his mother, there is no simple solution to soothe the pain of her absence. It is especially difficult since his father's health is deteriorating and their finances are tight.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. When difficulties come, he finds relief in spending time with friends and releasing his emotions in their presence. He occasionally confides in his brother, who always provides him with helpful advice and encouragement.

Dreams and Future Plans. He wanted to be financially stable and help his brother, aunt, and parents.

Daphne

Daphne is an 11-year-old female, a Grade 6 pupil. She lives with her grandfather and her six-year-old younger brother, with additional support from her aunt. The family primarily relies on financial assistance from Daphne's mother, who works abroad. Meanwhile, Daphne's father, who is involved with another woman, does not provide any financial support. Despite these challenges, Daphne's family strives to create a nurturing and stable environment for her and her brother.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She grew up without the presence of her parents but found solace in the nurturing care of her maternal grandfather. Reflecting on her upbringing, she fondly recalls a childhood imbued with joy, affection, and cherished moments.

Relationship with Peers. She labels her relationship with her peers as "good" due to the strong rapport she shared with them. However, there were times in her life when she

yearns for the presence of a complete family. However, this does not hinder her from forming friendships and finding enjoyment in her life.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She grappled with her emotions in the aftermath of her parents' breakup, lacking guidance and support. Feeling insecure, she struggled to express her feelings, even to her grandfather. She expressed, "I'll handle my issues solo if I have to." However, she would also try her best to communicate with her aunt or mother and express her problems or challenges that she is facing.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She expresses her intention to seek solace and encouragement from her friends to pursue happiness and joy, despite feeling sad and tired. She will confide in her aunt about her challenges, receiving both support and encouragement. Her aunt reassures her that she is capable of overcoming them.

Dreams and Future Plans. She expressed her desire to become a flight attendant and travel to various destinations worldwide. Her family encouraged her, noting that her height, slender physique, and beauty made her well-suited for the role. This encouragement motivated her to pursue a career as a flight attendant, enabling her to support and give back to those who have supported and guided her through life's challenges.

Elizabeth

Elizabeth is a 12-year-old female, a Grade 6 pupil. She resides with her grandparents, who provide for the household through the grandmother's pension from her career as a retired educator and the grandfather's income from operating a tricycle. When Elizabeth was eight, her mother remarried, and her father became involved in an extramarital affair. Both parents have contributed financially, with her mother's support being more substantial. However, Elizabeth has lacked emotional, physical, and mental nurturance from her parents, relying on her grandparents for stability and care.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She grew up without her parents by her side. She was raised and cared for by her grandparents on her father's side. She described her childhood with them as joyful, filled with love, appreciation, and beautiful memories. However, everything changed when her father was released from prison and visited home drunk, harassing her grandparents. This was the most traumatizing experience she had ever faced. Despite her father's troublesome behavior and her mother's decision to marry another man and left, she still longs for a happy and complete family, though she believes it may never be possible.

Relationship with Peers. She described her relationship with her peers as "okay, sometimes not okay" because she often felt alone, especially when she knew them with complete and happy families. At times, she wished her own family was not broken, feeling envious of theirs. As a result, she sometimes struggles with trust issues or having difficulty forming close bonds with her peers.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She experiences struggles with her emotions because she has no one to turn to for guidance and support after her parents broke up. She feels insecure and finds it difficult to communicate her emotions, even with her grandparents. She even said, "If I can still manage my problems, I will deal with it by myself."

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She would try various methods to find happiness whenever she faced hardships, like going back to the things that made her happy. Usually, she avoids discussing her troubles, but when they become too overwhelming, she would confide in her grandmother and seek her advice to navigate through life.

Dreams and Future Plans. She mentioned wanting her grandparents to live longer so that when she has a job in the future, she can give them whatever they like and provide them with opportunities to travel to different countries around the world.

Hyacinth

Hyacinth is an 11-year-old female, a Grade 5 pupil. Raised by her grandmother from birth, Hyacinth has grown up in a loving and nurturing environment. Her biological parents were not married, and she is the middle child of three siblings, each with different fathers. Her mother, who works in Malaysia, provides financial support for the family.

They all live together in their ancestral home, where Hyacinth shares a close bond with her aunt and two cousins. This extended family setup offers her a stable and supportive upbringing.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She smiles recalling how her grandmother loves her so much. They had a really close relationship. Nevertheless, she has not spent much time in contact with her birth mother. She had once inquired her mother about her biological father but was told nothing about him.

Relationship with Peers. She loves her brother very much, and they have many happy times together. Their relationship is one of great devotion. Even though they occasionally get into small arguments and even a few fights, as the day goes on, they always find comfort in each other's understanding, their disagreements dissolving in the warmth of their sibling love.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She grapples with insecurity, believing her mother favors her older brother. Managing these feelings proves challenging. Yet, she finds solace in her aunt, her mother's sister, who offers invaluable support. Trust is another hurdle; she fears her friends may gossip behind her back in her absence.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. When problems occur, she confides in her grandmother and aunt for guidance. Occasionally, she keeps personal problems to herself, believing they will eventually pass.

Dreams and Future Plans. She vows to shower her grandmother with abundant love and care, as she is resolute in ensuring her well-being. Believing herself to be the kind of person who will steadfastly stand by her grandma and aunt, offering them companionship and support when required, she finds her purpose in prioritizing her family's welfare. Her dedication to her loved ones instills in her a sense of purpose, motivating her to always prioritize their needs. For her, being there for her family is not just a duty but also a heartfelt expression of gratitude for their unwavering support and care over the years.

Junaida

Junaida is a 14-year-old female, currently a Grade 9 student. She lives with her grandmother in a low-income household. Since early childhood, Junaida's parents have been absent, having separated and each started new families.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She lives with her grandmother on her mother's side. Her grandmother with her aunts and uncles provides for her daily needs. According to her, she is treated like a princess in the household since she is the only girl among her cousins. Also, living with them is a family of her aunt with three boys. The household is considered as low-income but her father sends money to her, he even sent her an iPhone. So, all in all, she has a great life with her guardian, grandmother, as she described.

Relationship with Peers. The closest friends she has are mostly her classmates. Some of them are her blood relatives such as cousins. She has close friends but none of them is she considers as "barkada" since she has not much time for hanging out with a tight circle. She does not claim her situation to be better nor worse than her peers but she wishes her situation was the same as most children (growing up with both parents). She discloses that she had been to a fight once but for reason unrelated to her not being with biological parents.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She said she is experiencing typical problems of her age but none particular for being a child growing up with the absence of parental anchors.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She mentioned that she does not particularly struggle with the absence of parental figures, aside from occasional feelings of uneasiness when wishing her situation mirrored that of most children who grow up with both parents present.

Dreams and Future Plans. She reported that she wanted to finish schooling and join the military someday.

Loy

Loy is a 15-year-old male, a Grade 8 student. He lives with his grandparent in a fair-income household. Since toddlerhood, Loy's parents have been absent, having migrated for work. Despite their physical absence, his parents remain together and provide for the family from abroad. Loy's upbringing has been shaped by the care and support of his grandmother.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. He lives with his grandmother who raised him since he was a toddler. The boy shared that his grandmother stood as his parent almost all of the times in his life. Both of his biological parents migrated abroad to work. Although he was given a weekly allowance by his real parents, he would prefer living away from them and stay with his grandmother. He felt that his actions were always restricted and he felt awkward every time the real parents were around.

Relationship with Peers. The boy shared that he has a close circle of friends and has good terms with his classmates and peers. He has never been to a fight or in any case involving bullying and, in rare occasions, got into some quarrel for non-malicious teasing.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. Since his real parents give him a weekly allowance, he never ever had any financial issue. About his personal and academic life, he stated that his grandmother is always supportive for him.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. He admitted the he could not think of anything to share about personal coping with the challenges of having absent parents since he always has his grandmother and he has good relations with his peers and friends.

Dreams and Future Plans. Loy said he wanted to become an engineer or a lawyer someday.

May-may

May-may is a 14-year-old female, a Grade 8 student. She resides with her grandparents in a low-income household. Her parents separated and left when she was a toddler, each starting new families. Despite these early challenges, May-may has been raised in a loving and supportive environment provided by her grandparents, who ensure her well-being and education.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She lives with her grandparents on her mother's side. Her grandparents provide for her, the grandfather works as a construction worker with a minimum wage income and the grandmother attends their small sari-sari store. She stated that she loves her grandparents very much but she is closer to the grandfather than the grandmother for the reason that the grandfather always protects her and takes her side whenever the grandmother scolds or have arguments with her. She said that her grandparents treat her like a real daughter and she treats them like her real parents. She helps her grandparents in the household chores and taking care of their few livestock (goats, pigs, chickens, and ducks) at their backyard. She prefers living with the current guardians than with either parent.

Relationship with Peers. Her closest friends mainly consist of her classmates, with some of them being her blood relatives, such as cousins. While she values these friendships, she does not have a tight-knit "barkada" due to limited time for socializing. She does not perceive her situation as better as or worse than her peers', but she wishes she had grown up with both parents like most children. Although she has been in a fight before, it was unrelated to her family situation. She admits to harboring resentment towards her "Ate," an older cousin, who is in Grade 11 and lives with her in her grandparents' house, for the reason primarily involving household chores.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She mentioned experiencing typical challenges of her age, but none specifically relate to growing up without biological parents.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She mentioned not having any specific issues related to growing up without biological parents, although she occasionally feels uneasy when wishing her situation mirrored that of most children, who have real parents present.

Dreams and Future Plans. She said she wanted to finish schooling and become a soldier or a police officer someday.

Mikaela

Mikaela is a 12-year-old female, currently a Grade 6 pupil. She lives with her grandmother and maternal aunt, who both provide her with substantial support and care. The family depends on financial assistance from Mikaela's mother, who works in Manila. Her father, involved with another woman, does not contribute financially and Mikaela has never met him in person. Despite these challenges, Mikaela thrives in the nurturing environment created by her grandmother and aunt.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She is raised by her grandmother with assistance from her aunt, and her upbringing was described as "challenging" when it comes to expressing herself, given the lack of support from her guardians.

Relationship with Peers. Her friendships are good, but she tends to gravitate towards solitary moments, finding tranquility in her own company rather than engaging in extensive conversations with friends.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. She describes living in her home as both joyful and exasperating. She finds herself inexplicably upset with her family at times, leading her to believe she struggles with anger management. Additionally, she fears reprisal for expressing her emotions openly, adding to her internal turmoil. Another challenge she faces is financial instability.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. She rarely discusses her emotional stress until it becomes overwhelming. Seeking advice from her mother is extremely rare. She occasionally turns to her grandmother, affectionately called "mama." Her approach leans towards self-reliance, opting to tackle problems with determination and resourcefulness.

Dreams and Future Plans. She aspired to pursue a career as an artist. However, her guardians opposed her dream, insisting she become a nurse, citing concerns about financial stability in the arts. Consequently, she accepted and acknowledges their wishes, intending to secure employment and assist with their financial obligations in the future.

Rendelou

Rendelou is a 14-year-old male, currently a Grade 7 student. He was raised and nurtured by his paternal aunt, who stepped in to care for him after his parents separated when he was very young. Being her only charge, Rendelou received undivided attention and care from his aunt, who did not have children of her own. Unfortunately, he lacked support from his parents, both financially and emotionally, throughout his upbringing. The family primarily relied on his aunt's income from her job as a public-school teacher to sustain the household. Rendelou admitted that he was gay.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. His reminiscence of childhood with his guardian were vivid. He fondly recalls a time when worries were few and happiness were abundant. As he come to age, he conceals his true identity, unable to express himself to his aunt for fear of rejection if she will discover his homosexuality.

Relationship with Peers. He characterizes his rapport with his peers as strained due to frequent clashes arising from his behavior. He emphasized that his voice was often unheard at home, leading him to assert himself by acting in a manner aligned with his own desires,

adopting or choosing to align his self with a particular viewpoint, approach, or behavior "I'll do what feels right for me, regardless of others' reactions."

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. Financially, his aunt provides ample support, but emotionally, he experiences a lack of openness in their household. He describes it as a situation where children are expected to remain quiet while adults converse, leaving little room for their voices to be heard.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. His way of coping involves sharing his feelings beyond his immediate family circle. He discusses his life worries with those he trusts deeply, such as a close friend with whom he feels authentic, and his Araling Panlipunan (Social Studies) teacher. Occasionally, he confides in his aunt, though he tends to avoid delving into deeply personal or emotional topics with her.

Dreams and Future Plans. He is yet undecided about his future profession, though he planned to complete his education so that he could secure a good job, enabling him to repay his aunt for all her support and provide himself with the comfort of life she had always wanted for him.

Sofia

Sofia, an 11-year-old Grade 5 student, faced upheaval when her parents were detained for drug-related issue, leading to her and her little brother's placement in the care of their father's sister. Terrified and depressed by the ordeal, Sofia found solace in her aunt's unwavering kindness and support. Despite the challenges, her aunt provides for their needs, guiding Sofia through the turmoil and helping her make sense of the circumstances.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians. She recalls her aunt's generosity and affection toward her and her brother. They frequently go out with their cousins to have fun. Her aunt is the first to comfort her whenever she starts sobbing when she misses her parents.

Relationship with Peers. She is close with her brother and their cousins. Though they occasionally quarrel and get into fights, they always make up and reestablish their friendship.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors. Although she is close with her brother and their cousins, they would get into some quarrel sometimes. She struggles in conflict resolution and emotional regulation when these quarrels with her brother and their cousins come.

Coping Mechanisms on Challenges. Sometimes, when faced with difficulties, she would figure them out on her own and cry. She has times when she would feel overburdened and would have to take care of everything by herself. On some occasions, she would speak with her aunt and her closest friend. She would feel better after talking to them about her concerns and issues. Her aunt would give her consoling counsel and assurance, and her best friend is there to listen and encourage her at all times. She would feel less alone and able to deal with her problems, thanks to these talks.

Dreams and Future Plans. She aims to support her aunt by meeting her needs and showing her with the same kindness she received when she starts her own family in the future. She is determined to repay her aunt's kindness, recalling the love and support she received during challenging times. Her goal is to ensure her aunt has everything she needs

and feels appreciated as an adult. She intends to treat her aunt with the same love and support she received, motivated by her gratitude and respect for her aunt's past generosity.

4.2. Findings

Presented herein are the analyses and interpretation of the results obtained from the semi-structured interview on the participants vis-à-vis the main research questions.

What are the childhood experiences of children with their caregivers or guardians?

The children experience various dynamics with their caregivers or guardians and navigate their childhoods with unique challenges and coping mechanisms:

Alyssa, Chloe, and Sofia find comfort in the care provided by their aunts during their parents' absence due to work or incarceration. Despite the longing for their parents, they appreciate the love and support they receive from their extended family.

Cyrill and Hyacinth cherish the nurturing environment provided by their aunts and grandparents, respectively, in the absence of parental figures. They build strong bonds with siblings and cousins, finding solace and support within their family circle.

Daphne, Elizabeth, May-may, and Mikaela face emotional struggles stemming from parental separation or absence. While Daphne seeks solace in her grandfather and aunt, Elizabeth finds stability in her grandparents but grapples with past traumas. May-may yearns for a complete family but finds solace in her grandparents' love, while Mikaela navigates her emotions with limited support from her grandmother and aunt.

Loy and Junaida experience financial stability from their absent parents but lack emotional support. Loy thrives under his grandmother's care, while Junaida seeks companionship among friends and dreams of joining the military.

Rendelou struggles with his identity as a gay adolescent and finds limited emotional support in his aunt's household. Despite financial stability, he feels unheard and turns to trusted friends and teachers for guidance.

The children exhibit resilience and adaptability, drawing strength from their familial bonds and finding ways to cope with their challenges, whether through seeking support from caregivers, confiding in friends, or pursuing personal aspirations for a better future.

How do children describe their relationship with peers in the absence of parental anchor?

Based on the responses, children describe their relationships with peers in the absence of parental anchors in various ways, influenced by their individual circumstances and coping mechanisms:

Alyssa maintains a close bond with her siblings and occasionally feels a deep longing for her parents during disagreements. She finds comfort in confiding in her aunt and pursues solutions independently while accepting responsibility for her actions.

Despite living with cousins, Chloe feels better off alone with her grandmother and aunt. She experiences occasional loneliness and envy towards peers with complete families but consoles herself by recognizing the love and support she receives from her family.

Cyrill shares a strong bond with his brother and cousins, finding relief from the absence of parental anchors by spending time with friends and confiding in his brother for advice and encouragement.

Despite struggling with her parents' breakup, Daphne maintains good relationships with her peers and seeks solace and encouragement from her aunt and friends to overcome challenges.

Elizabeth feels alone at times and struggles with trust issues and forming close bonds with peers. She copes by occasionally confiding in her grandmother and expressing gratitude for her support.

Hyacinth shares a close bond with her brother and aunt, finding support and stability in her extended family. She confides in her grandmother and aunt during challenging times and expresses a desire to repay their kindness in the future.

Junaida maintains good relationships with classmates and cousins but wishes for a more typical family structure. She experiences occasional feelings of uneasiness but does not face specific challenges related to the absence of parental anchors.

Loy has a supportive grandmother and good relationships with friends. He does not experience significant challenges related to the absence of his parents and focuses on his future aspirations.

May-may values her friendships but wishes for a complete family like her peers. She experiences occasional uneasiness but copes by focusing on her education and future goals. Mikaela finds solace in her own company and struggles with expressing herself due to a lack of support from her guardians. She copes by relying on her determination and resourcefulness to tackle challenges.

Renelou's relationships with peers are strained, and he struggles with feeling unheard at home. He copes by sharing his feelings with trusted individuals and intends to repay his aunt for her support in the future.

Sofia maintains close relationships with her brother and cousins but struggles with conflict resolution and emotional regulation. She copes by confiding in her aunt and best friend, finding comfort and reassurance through their support.

Despite facing challenges such as loneliness, envy, and trust issues, the children maintain strong bonds with siblings, cousins, and friends. They find solace in confiding in caregivers, seeking support from friends, and focusing on future aspirations. Overall, the children exhibit resilience and adaptability in navigating their circumstances, emphasizing the importance of familial and social support in overcoming challenges.

What are the challenges of children in the absence of parental anchors?

The challenges faced by children in the absence of parental anchors encompass a range of emotional, social, and practical difficulties, as revealed in the narratives of the participants. These challenges significantly impact their well-being and development, highlighting the need for targeted support and interventions to address their unique circumstances.

Emotional Struggles. One prominent challenge experienced by these children is emotional instability and insecurity stemming from the absence of parental figures. Alyssa, Chloe, Cyrill, Daphne, Elizabeth, Hyacinth, and Sofia all express feelings of loneliness, longing, and inadequacy, yearning for the love and guidance of their parents. They grapple with a sense of loss and sadness, compounded by the absence of nurturing relationships fundamental to their emotional growth.

Social Isolation. Children living without parental anchors often face challenges in forming and maintaining relationships with peers. Chloe, Daphne, Elizabeth, Hyacinth, Junaida, and Mikaela struggle with feelings of loneliness and envy as they observe their peers with intact families. They long for the companionship and support of a complete family unit, feeling isolated and disconnected from their peers who enjoy the presence of both parents.

Financial Instability. Practical obstacles also arise in the absence of parental anchors, including financial instability and limited access to resources. While some children, like Alyssa and Sofia, benefit from the support of extended family members, others, such as Chloe, Elizabeth, and May-may, face financial constraints and struggle to meet their basic needs. The absence of parental guidance further complicates their ability to navigate financial challenges and plan for their future.

Parental Absence and Role Modeling. Moreover, the lack of parental figures deprives children of positive role models and mentors to guide their behavior and decision-making. Rendelou, for instance, experiences a strained relationship with his peers due to a lack of emotional support and openness in his household. Without parental guidance, children may struggle to develop essential life skills and moral values, leading to feelings of insecurity and uncertainty about their future.

How do children cope with the challenges encountered in the absence of parental anchors?

The children demonstrate resilience, relying on familial support and personal determination to navigate the challenges of growing up without parental anchors. Their coping mechanisms vary, but they all share a common goal of building a better future for themselves and their caregivers.

Seeking Support from Caregivers and Family. Alyssa, Cyrill, Daphne, Elizabeth, Hyacinth, and Sofia all demonstrate a reliance on their caregivers or family members for support and guidance when facing challenges. They confide in them, seek reassurance, and find solace in their presence.

Independence and Self-Reliance. Alyssa and Sofia exhibit coping mechanisms that involve pursuing solutions independently and accepting responsibility for their actions. They deal with problems on their own to some extent before seeking external support.

Finding Comfort in Relationships. Chloe, Cyrill, Daphne, Elizabeth, and Hyacinth derive emotional support from their relationships with siblings, cousins, and peers. These connections offer them companionship and understanding during difficult times.

Resilience and Determination. Despite their individual circumstances, all the children display resilience and determination in coping with their challenges. They face adversity with courage and perseverance, striving to overcome obstacles and achieve their goals.

What are the dreams and future plans of children living with their caregivers or guardians?

The dreams and future plans of children living with caregivers or guardians highlight several common themes:

Gratitude and Reciprocity. Many children express gratitude towards their caregivers and aspire to repay their kindness in the future.

Financial Independence and Stability. There is a prevalent desire among the children to achieve financial stability and independence to overcome current challenges.

Career Aspirations and Goals. Various career aspirations are evident among the children, reflecting their hopes for personal and professional fulfillment.

Family Support and Unity. Despite family disruptions, the children value the support and unity within their extended families.

Personal Growth and Development. Each child aims for personal growth and development, striving to better their circumstances and those of their families.

Resilience and Determination. Despite facing challenges, the children exhibit resilience and determination in pursuing their dreams and creating better futures.

In essence, these themes underscore the resilience, gratitude, and aspirations of children in challenging circumstances as they work towards brighter futures.

Summary

The findings underscore the resilience and adaptability of children facing familial adversity, highlighting the pivotal role of extended family members or guardians in providing stability, care, and guidance. While challenges such as emotional struggles and societal comparisons persist, participants demonstrate a remarkable capacity for coping and maintaining hopeful outlooks for the future.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1. Conclusion

The study explored the experiences and coping mechanisms of children growing up without parental anchors, relying on extended family members or guardians for support. Through qualitative analysis of individual narratives, common themes emerged regarding their relationships, challenges, coping mechanisms, and dreams for the future.

Experiences with Caregivers or Guardians

Across participants, strong bonds were evident with the individuals providing care, ranging from aunts, uncles, grandparents, and other blood-related guardians. Despite the absence of biological parents, many children expressed gratitude and affection for their caregivers, highlighting instances of love, support, and financial provision.

Relationship with Peers

Participants demonstrated varying degrees of social interaction, with some having close relationships with siblings and cousins, while others found solace in friendships outside the family circle. However, challenges such as envy or conflicts with peers were noted, stemming from the desire for a complete family structure.

Challenges in the Absence of Parental Anchors

Emotional struggles, feelings of loneliness, and yearning for parental presence were common among the participants. Instances of insecurity, envy, and difficulty in expressing emotions were noted, often linked to societal perceptions and comparisons with peers from intact families.

Coping Mechanisms

Children employed various coping strategies, including seeking solace in family members, confiding in trusted individuals, pursuing personal interests, and finding resilience in self-reliance. While some shared their concerns openly, others struggled with communication barriers or internalized their emotions.

Dreams and Future Plans

Despite their challenges, participants expressed aspirations for the future, ranging from academic and career goals to desires for familial stability and reciprocation of support. Motivated by gratitude and a sense of duty, many aimed to repay their caregivers' kindness and create better futures for themselves and their families.

5.2. Recommendations

With careful considerations, based on the findings, analyses and discussions, the researchers arrived at sound recommendations for the caregivers and/or guardians of LBC and/or orphans, as well as, the teachers, counselors, social workers, service providers, policy-makers, and other related field.

Supportive Interventions

Implement programs aimed at bolstering emotional resilience and coping skills among children growing up without parental anchors, emphasizing the importance of open communication and seeking support from trusted individuals.

Family Strengthening Initiatives

Foster community-based initiatives that promote familial bonds and provide resources for extended families caring for children in the absence of biological parents, including access to counseling, financial assistance, and parenting support.

Education and Awareness

Raise awareness within communities and schools about the diverse family structures and experiences of children, promoting empathy, inclusivity, and support for those facing familial challenges.

Policy Advocacy

Advocate for policies that prioritize the welfare of children in non-traditional family setups, ensuring access to essential services, legal protections, and opportunities for holistic development.

By addressing these recommendations, stakeholders can contribute to fostering supportive environments and empowering children to navigate and thrive despite the absence of parental anchors.

5.3. Note for Future Research

While this study provides valuable insights into the experiences and coping mechanisms of children growing up without parental anchors, it is essential to acknowledge certain limitations that may impact the generalizability and depth of the findings. Future research in this area should consider the following:

Sample Characteristics

The participants in this study were drawn from specific demographics and cultural contexts, potentially limiting the applicability of the findings to broader populations. Future studies should aim for more diverse samples to capture a wider range of experiences and perspectives.

Qualitative Nature

The qualitative nature of this study allowed for in-depth exploration of individual narratives. However, the subjective nature of qualitative data collection and analysis may introduce bias or overlook certain aspects of the participants' experiences. Combining qualitative approaches with quantitative methods could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

Self-Reporting Bias

Participants' responses may be influenced by social desirability bias or memory recall limitations, affecting the accuracy and completeness of their accounts. Future research could employ triangulation methods or longitudinal designs to validate and supplement self-reported data.

Limited Scope

This study focused primarily on the experiences and coping mechanisms of children without parental anchors, overlooking the perspectives of caregivers or other family members involved in their upbringing. Exploring the dynamics and interactions within the extended family unit could offer additional insights into the support networks and challenges faced by children in non-traditional family structures.

Contextual Factors

The socio-cultural, economic, and environmental contexts in which children grow up play a significant role in shaping their experiences and coping strategies. Future research should consider contextual factors such as cultural norms, socioeconomic status, and community resources to provide a more nuanced understanding of the phenomenon.

Addressing these limitations in future research endeavors will contribute to a more robust and comprehensive understanding of the experiences and needs of children growing up without parental anchors, ultimately informing the development of more effective interventions and support systems for this vulnerable population.

Acknowledgements

The authors sincerely thank the participants of this study, whose openness and willingness to share their experiences made this research possible. Their contributions

provided invaluable insights, and their trust and cooperation were essential to the success of this work.

The gratitude is also extended to Dr. Mary Jane B. Omandam, Vice President for Administration at Saint Columban College and instructor of Marital and Family Counseling, for her invaluable support and guidance throughout this study.

And most of all, praise be all to the God Almighty! Panagdait to all of His creation!

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this research. The research was conducted independently, and there are no financial or personal relationships with any individuals or organizations that could have inappropriately influenced or biased the work.

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